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First record of *Tephritis praecox* (Diptera: Tephritidae), a pest of *Calendula* (Asteraceae), in the mainland Ukraine, with remarks on its distribution

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Korneyev, S. V., Mykytiuk, T. P., Bachynskiy, A., Korneyev, V. A. First record of *Tephritis praecox* (Diptera: Tephritidae), a pest of *Calendula* (Asteraceae), in the mainland Ukraine, with remarks on its distribution. — The marigold fly *Tephritis praecox* (Loew, 1844) is recorded for the first time from the western part of Ukraine; it was unintentionally introduced with the seed / flower heads of its host plant. Data on its distribution are summarised and discussed.

Key words. Tephritidae, Ukraine, marigold, *Calendula*, pest, introduced species.

Корнєєв, С. В., Микитюк, Т. П., Бачинський, А., Корнєєв, В. О. Перша реєстрація *Tephritis praecox* (Diptera: Tephritidae), шкідника нагідок (*Calendula*, Asteraceae), на материковій частині України, із зауваженнями щодо поширення. — Нагідкова муха *Tephritis praecox* (Loew, 1844) вперше зареєстрована із західної частини України; вона була ненавмисно інтродукована з насінням/квітковими головками кормової рослини. Узагальнено та обговорено дані щодо її поширення.

Ключові слова. Tephritidae, Україна, нагідки, *Calendula*, шкідник, інтродукований вид.

Introduction

The marigold fly, *Tephritis praecox* (Loew, 1844), was previously known to occur mainly in Mediterranean and Atlantic European countries from Great Britain to Greece and Ukraine (Crimean Peninsula), as well as in North Africa and the Middle East (Norrbom et al. 1999; Merz & Korneyev, 2004). The larvae of *T. praecox* feed in flower heads of *Calendula arvensis* and *C. officinalis* (Asteraceae). *Tephritis praecox* represents a sister group to the other *Tephritis* species (Korneyev et al., 2020). The exact origin of its host plant, *Calendula*, is not known, as this plant has been cultivated for medicinal and food purposes for several thousand years, but as the centre of diversity of the tribe Calenduleae is in southern Africa, an African origin seems the most reliable hypothesis. *Tephritis praecox* and *T. poecilura* Loew, 1869 were considered to be separate species because of the yellow/black colouration of the fem-

ora and base of the abdomen, as well as minor differences in their wing patterns; Merz (1992) showed by studying material reared on its host plant that they are merely conspecific colour morphs.

In Ukraine, the species was previously known to occur on the Crimean peninsula, but not on the mainland.

Recently, *T. praecox* has been recorded as a pest of cultivated *Calendula officinalis* in Slovakia, not far from Ukraine (Korneyev et al., 2021). It was therefore expected that the species could be found in Ukraine under similar conditions, and it was soon recorded from the Ternopil region by TPM and AB.

In this paper we summarise the known data on its distribution based on literature references and collection material examined by SVK and published as a dataset (Korneyev, 2023).

Tephritis praecox* (Loew, 1844)Trypeta praecox* Loew, 1844: 391.

Tephritis praecox: Loew, 1862: 102; Hendel, 1927: 194; Séguay, 1934: 163; Korneyev, 1987: 87; Freidberg, Kugler, 1989: 129; Merz, 1992: 228, 1993: 118, 1994: 74; Norrbom et al., 1999: 218; Korneyev, Dirlbek, 2001: 475; Yaran, Kütük, 2015: 1061, 2016: 791; Ebejer, Gatt, 2021: 42; Korneyev et al., 2021: 33; Mazzon, Korneyev, 2021; Yaran et al., 2021: 2235; Görmez, Kütük, 2022: 727; Kettani et al., 2022: 266.

Tephritis poecilura Loew, 1869: 21; Hendel, 1927: 193; Freidberg, Kugler, 1989: 126; Merz, 1992.

Material examined. Type. Lectotype *Trypeta praecox*: ♀; Греція: “Rhodes” (Coll. H. Loew) (MNKB). Holotype *Tephritis poecilura*: 1 ♂: “Spanien, v. Seidlitz” (MNKB). **Non-type.** Azerbaijan: “Margushevan nr Terter”, 26.05.1935, 1♀; 10–11.06.1935, 1♂, 1♀; 10–11.06.1935, 1♂; 26.10.1935, 1♂, 8♀; 4–13.11.1935, 7♂, 5♀; (Veltishchev) (ZISP); Cyprus: Porodhromos, 1400–1600 m, 18.06.1971, 1♂, 2♀ (M. J. & J. P. Dufels) (RMNH); Greece: “Graecia, v. Kiesenw.” 9♂, 5♀ (Coll. H. Loew) (MNKB); Crete, Om Vethianus 16.04.1991, 1♀; 420 m Larani, 21.04.1991, 1♀; 530 m, Kamares 21.04.1991, 1♂; 500 m Kato 22.04.1991, 1♂ (Merz & Eggenberger) (ZISP); Sterea, prov. Fokida, Hrisom Amfissa, Village, 250 m, 38°28.9' N 22°27.9' E, 19.04.2003, 1♀ (C. Lange & J. Ziegler) (MNKB); Litochoro, Olympus, h=800–850 m, 7.06.2002, 1♂, 2♀ (S. & V.Korneyev, E. Kameneva) (SIZK); Georgia: “Tiflis” [=Tbilisi], 05.1903, 1♀ (K. Satunin) (ZISP); Iran: E. Azerb., rd. near Youzband, 38°44.41' N 47°06.1' E, h=1580 m, 17.05.2014, 2♂, 4♀ (S. & V.Korneyev) (SIZK); E. Azerb., Howrand, 38°46.08' N 47°05.52' E, h=1725 m, 17.05.2014, 7♂, 4♀ (S. & V. Korneyev) (SIZK); Qazvin, wetland at waterfall, 36°21.50' N 50°03.42' E, h = 1500 m, 7.06.2014, 1♂ (S. & V.Korneyev) (SIZK); East Azerbaijan Province: Dizmar Protected Area, Chichakli val., 38°40.50' N 46°32.05' E, h = 2215 m, 26.06.2014, 1♂ (S. & V.Korneyev) (SIZK); Spain: Andalusia, 2♀ (Staudinger) (ZISP); La Palma, 47471. IV. 4♂ (Becker) (MNKB); Andalusien, Algeciras, 1♂, 1♀ (Strobl) (MNKB); Kazakhstan: Turkestan, 2♂, 1♀ (MNKB); Kyrgyzstan: “Pishpek” [=Bishkek], 29.06.1925, 1♀ (Rohdendorf) (ZISP); Morocco: Haut-Atlas, 1900 m, Tizi n'Test S, 29–30.06.1987, 2 ♀ (W. Schacht) (ZSSM); Slovakia Trebišov, 48.607589°N, 21.718052°E, ex flower heads of *Calendula officinalis*, 14–17.10.2021, 15♂, 16♀ (I. Šalamon) (SIZK); Switzerland:

Geneve, Collonge-Bellerive, 5.08.1966, 1 ♂ (P. P. Babiy & Dolden) (ZSSM); Tadjikistan: 5 km SW Adrasman, Qurama Ridge, Karamaza Mt. [40.63 N, 69.94 E], 22.05.1989, 2♂, 1♀ (Volkovich) (ZISP); Tunisia: Manassy, 11.1928, 11♂, 4♀ (C. Dumont) (MHNP); Ukraine, Crimea: Karadagh, 25.07.1984, 1♂ [Budashkin]; Sudak District, vic. Morskoe, Bashennyi [Agira] cape [44.813889, 34.745833], 15.09.2011, 2♂ (Yu. Guglya) (SIZK); Uzbekistan: Samarkand Region, Kattakurgan District, Kumak, 21.05.1929, 2♂ (L. Zimin) (ZISP).

In November 2023, several specimens were surprisingly reared from the flower heads of marigolds planted for 3 years in Ternopil Region: Nyrkiv (48.8113 N, 25.5971 E). These flies were photographed (Figs 1–2) by TPM, uploaded on UkrBIN (2023) site by AB and identified from photos by VAK; identification was confirmed by SVK. The flies were apparently introduced to the mainland Ukraine with the seeds of unknown origin.

Distribution: Albania, Austria, Afghanistan, Azerbaijan, Belgium, Bulgaria, Cyprus, France, Georgia, Greece, Hungary, Iran, Italy (peninsular, Sicily, Sardinia), Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Morocco, the Netherlands, Romania, Spain (peninsular, Canary Is.), Switzerland, Tajikistan, Tunisia, Turkey, Ukraine, Uzbekistan, United Kingdom (Merz, 1992; Merz, Korneyev, 2004; Korneyev, 2016), Portugal (peninsular, Madeira) (Smit, 2006), N Iran (Mohamadzade Namin, Korneyev, 2018); Algeria (El Harym, Belqat, 2017), Malta (Ebejer, Gatt, 2021), Slovakia (Korneyev et al., 2021).

Host plants: the larva develops in the inflorescences of *Calendula arvensis* (Freidberg, Kugler, 1989) and *C. officinalis*. A report of *Filago gallica* (Mik, 1880: 597) as the host plant apparently refers to another species of the tribe Tephritini.

Figs. 1–2. A female emerged from flower heads of *Calendula* (photo by T. P. Mykytiuk).

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Fig. 3. Distribution of *Tephritis praecox* (map is generated from the UkrBIN Dataset (Korneyev, 2023)).

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